

TECHNOLOGY OF SILICATE BRICK PRODUCTION

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Abstract. For the concrete industry to be sustainable, using waste glass instead of natural resources is one of the best alternatives. In order to solve environmental problems caused by production waste, other materials are used in concrete production. The use of waste glass in the production of concrete not only brings great benefits to the environment, but also increases the shelf life of concrete when used in optimal quantities. This article covers the technology of using waste glass as an alternative material used as a partial replacement of fine aggregates in the production of new mortar.

Keywords. Mortar, cement, sand, compressive strength, waste glass replacement.

Аннотация. Чтобы бетонная промышленность была устойчивой, использование отходов стекла вместо природных ресурсов является одной из лучших альтернатив. Для решения экологических проблем, вызванных отходами производства, в производстве бетона используются другие материалы. Использование отходов стекла в производстве бетона не только приносит большую пользу окружающей среде, но и увеличивает срок годности бетона при использовании в оптимальных количествах. В данной статье рассматривается технология использования отходов стекла в качестве альтернативного материала, применяемого в качестве частичной замены мелких заполнителей при производстве новых строительных растворов.

Ключевые слова. Раствор, цемент, песок, прочность на сжатие, замена стеклобоя.

In developing countries, the main problem is environmental pollution due to the increase in household and industrial waste. Disposal of waste, especially domestic and industrial glass waste, has become a major problem. In recent years, due to the growth of industrialization and the rapid improvement of living

standards, the amount of glass waste is increasing. For these reasons, this study was conducted through basic experimental studies to analyze the potential of crushed glass waste as fine aggregates in mortar. If waste materials produced in large quantities are used instead of natural materials in the construction industry: we will have advantages such as saving natural resources and eliminating waste materials.

Research on the production and use of products and structures made of these materials in construction shows that, compared to traditional materials of the same purpose and quality, they are the most effective and promising, with less investment in the organization of production and material consumption and fuel and energy resources, cheap raw materials will be consumed and the opportunity to use industrial waste will appear. It serves to introduce resource-saving, energy-saving and zero-waste technologies, which are becoming increasingly relevant over time, taking into account the global paradigm of greening production and construction.

Modern products of this production are divided into two groups of materials that are fundamentally different in terms of their main properties (density, strength, frost resistance, etc.), technological parameters of production, and the structure of the final product. The first group consists of concrete, which is obtained by forming porous mixtures and products of various configurations and purposes (blocks, slabs, wall panels, cladding panels, etc.). The second group includes silicate bricks, stones, blocks and partition plates, which are formed by pressing the initial mixture. Recently, the nomenclature and fields of application of compressed silicate products have undergone significant changes in the direction of expansion. Unfortunately, a wide range of specialists are not sufficiently aware of new products, their properties, and the possibilities of their use in the construction of buildings and structures in various working conditions.

The load-bearing capacity of walls made of hollow silicate bricks does not differ from walls made of solid bricks, and the thermal conductivity of the structure made of hollow products decreases accordingly. This allows them to be used with high efficiency for the construction of not only external, but also internal parts and walls. Especially promising is the combination of building envelopes made of silicate bricks with load-bearing structures made of dense products and partitions made of dense silicate blocks with high sound insulation.

It should be noted that, unlike ordinary brick products, pressed materials (bricks and masonry) can combine the necessary load-bearing capacity while

maintaining aesthetic expressiveness due to the painting of materials and hydrophobic surface treatment.

Silicate products have high weather resistance. Despite conflicting information on the water resistance of sand-lime bricks, modern materials produced on a large scale by enterprises fully meet the requirements of regulatory documents and can withstand long-term exposure to groundwater (or in simulation) exhibits good stability. Many full-scale tests have proven that the strength of silicate materials increases as a result of the carbonization effect due to the formation of insoluble calcium carbonates, which close the pores and voids of the product. Silicate brick has a good margin of safety, which ensures its durability at high temperatures.

Thus, despite a slight decrease in market indicators associated with objective general economic and geopolitical factors, interest in silicate bricks as an object of various scientific and practical studies does not decrease. At the same time, it is clear that it is necessary to combine the efforts and capabilities of enterprises capable of forming tasks for improving technological processes in order to increase the competitiveness of sand-lime bricks and increase the demand for finished products. It is also important that the results of scientific research and development are not left on paper, and that the most promising ones are put into production. World experience shows that enterprises that keep pace with the development of science and technology achieve the best commercial results.

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